

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS. PART I. COPPER BIGUANIDINES.

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The free anhydrous cupric biguanidine has been obtained from the hydrated variety. This furnishes an additional evidence in support of the constitution of these complexes, previously suggested. It has been further shown that the formation of complexes with biguanide confers great stability on many unstable simple cupric salts like iodide, sulphite, thiosulphate, thiocyanate and hypophosphite. Besides these, a number of other new cupric bisbiguanidinium salts, such as fluoride, bromide, nitrite, carbonate, dithionate and chromate, has been described.

Certain complex compounds of biguanide and its substitution products with bivalent metals like copper, nickel and cobalt have been described from very early times. Rathke (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 779) prepared simple copper biguanide sulphate and formulated it as $(C_2N_5H_6)_2Cu \cdot H_2SO_4$. Emich (*Monatsh.*, 1883, 4, 395) prepared copper derivatives of ethylbiguanide sulphate by the action of copper sulphate on dicyandiamide dissolved in ethylamine. Smolka and Friedrich (*ibid.*, 1888, 9, 227) subsequently isolated phenylbiguanide derivatives of cobalt, copper and nickel. Rudolf Ziegelbauer (*Monatsh.*, 1896, 17, 648) prepared *ortho*-phenylenebiguanide derivatives of cobalt and nickel (*cf.* Dubsy, Langer and Strand, *Collection*, 1938, 10, 112). Finally R. Andreasch (*Monatsh.*, 1927, 48, 145) prepared copper biguanide hydrochloride and nitrate by the addition of biguanide chloride and nitrate on ammoniacal copper chloride and nitrate respectively. With each atom of the bivalent metal two molecules of biguanide were found to be associated. The constitution of complex compounds of biguanide with bivalent metals has already been discussed by Rây and Saha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 15).

In the present paper a number of complex copper biguanide salts has been described besides the free hydrated and anhydrous base. Co-ordination with the biguanide molecule has been found to confer stability to many unstable simple salts of copper, such as the iodide, sulphite, thiocyanate, hypophosphite and thiosulphate, which, as is well known, readily change into the cuprous state under ordinary circumstances. Besides these, fluoride, chloride, bromide, dithionate, chromate, carbonate, nitrate and nitrite of the complex copper biguanide base have been prepared and their properties studied. Of these the copper biguanide hydrate, chloride, nitrate and sulphate, as already stated, have been described by previous workers.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cupric bisbiguanide dihydrate was prepared in the form of bright red silky plates from ammoniacal copper sulphate solution and an alkaline solution of biguanide sulphate as described by Herth (*Ber.*, 1880, 13, 1358). The substance was dried over caustic potash to a constant weight. {Found : N, 46.77; Cu, 21.31; H₂O (by loss at 110°), 11.95. [Cu(Big)₂].2H₂O requires N, 46.73; Cu, 21.22; H₂O, 12.01 per cent} where BigH = one biguanide molecule.

The substance readily absorbs carbon dioxide from air, liberates ammonia from hot ammonium chloride solution and combines with two equivalents of hydrochloric acid to form the chloride. It thus behaves as a diacidic base.

Cupric bisBiguanidine.—When the dihydrate was heated to 110° for 14 hours it lost the whole of its water. {Found : N, 52.93; Cu, 24.0. [Cu(Big)₂] requires N, 53.11; Cu, 24.12 per cent}.

Cupric bisBiguanidinium Chloride.—When the powdered base was heated with 15% ammonium chloride solution to 60°-70° for some time on the water-bath, it dissolved with evolution of ammonia. The solution was filtered hot and on cooling pure crystals of the chloride separated from the filtrate. These were washed first with ice-cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. The salt can also be prepared by treating the base with dilute hydrochloric acid. The substance forms red needle-shaped crystals, readily soluble in water. It decomposes on treatment with dilute acids. The same salt was prepared also by R. Andreasch (*loc. cit.*) from ammoniacal copper chloride solution and biguanide hydrochloride. {Found : N, 37.44; Cl, 19.18; Cu, 17.02; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 9.59. [X] Cl₂. 2H₂O requires N, 37.57; Cl, 19.06; Cu, 17.07; H₂O, 9.66 per cent} where X = [Cu(BigH⁺)₂].

Equivalent Conductivity at 35°.

<i>v</i> (litres)	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_v ...	104.6	115.2	127.5	129.0	131.6	135.3	141.6
λ_∞ ...	140.8	143.1	149.6	144.7	142.9	143.5	147.7
(from Walden's formula)				λ_∞ (mean) = 144.6			

Therefore, the mobility of $1/2$ [Cu(BigH⁺)₂] = 144.6 - 66.7 = 77.9, the mobility of chlorine ion being 66.7.

Cryoscopic Measurements.

Subs./100 g. of water (on the anhydrous basis).	Depression in °C. Δ	Mol. wt. m.	van't Hoff's factor $i = M/m$.	Degree of dis- sociation. $a = i - 1/n - 1$
0.5483	0.083	119.0	2.83	0.91
0.2741	0.041	120.3	2.80	0.90

The result shows that even at 0° the substance is dissociated almost completely into three ions and the whole of the chlorine is in the ionic state.

When heated to 105° for 4 hours, the salt lost the whole of its water. The anhydrous chloride gave {Found: Cl, 20.86; Cu, 18.82. $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Cl}_2$ requires Cl, 21.09; Cu, 18.89 per cent}. The bluish violet anhydrous chloride readily absorbs water to regenerate the hydrated compound.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium bromide was obtained by heating the base with chemically pure ammonium bromide on the water-bath at about 80° until a clear solution resulted. The solution was filtered hot by suction. The crystals obtained by cooling the filtrate were filtered, washed and dried as described above. It forms brick-red needle-shaped crystals and resembles the chloride in properties. {Found: N, 30.24; Br, 34.58; Cu, 13.75. $[\text{X}]\text{Br}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 30.34; Br, 34.63; Cu, 13.78 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium iodide was prepared from the complex base and ammonium iodide as described in the previous case. The substance forms red needle-shaped crystals much less soluble in water than the other halides. {Found: N, 24.52; I, 44.39; Cu, 11.18. $[\text{X}]\text{I}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 24.40; I, 44.28; Cu, 11.08 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium fluoride was prepared like the previous compounds from the base and the neutral ammonium fluoride. It is more soluble than the other halides and forms red needle-shaped crystals. {Found: N, 37.35; F, 10.24; Cu, 17.06. $[\text{X}]\text{F}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 37.27; F, 10.11; Cu, 16.93 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium nitrate, as in the case of previous compounds, was obtained from the base and ammonium nitrate in the form of pale rose crystals, sparingly soluble in cold water. It can also be prepared by adding a solution of ammonium nitrate to a concentrated solution of the chloride. The same substance was also prepared by Andreasch (*loc. cit.*) from ammoniacal copper nitrate solution and biguanide nitrate. {Found: N (total), 39.68; Cu, 15.03; NO_2 , 29.27. $[\text{X}](\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 39.47; Cu, 14.94; NO_2 , 29.13 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium nitrite was prepared by adding a solution of sodium nitrite to a concentrated solution of the chloride. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. It resembles the nitrate in colour and, like the latter, is sparingly soluble in water. {Found: N(total), 45.17; Cu, 16.79;

NO_2 , 24'37. [X] $(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 44'72; Cu, 16'93; NO_2 , 24'49 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium carbonate was precipitated by adding a solution of sodium carbonate to a concentrated solution of the chloride. {Found: N, 35'02; Cu, 16'07; CO_3 , 15'33. [X] $\text{CO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 35'11; Cu, 15'99; CO_3 , 15'09 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium sulphite was prepared by adding, drop by drop, a cold concentrated, freshly prepared solution of sodium sulphite to a cold saturated solution of the chloride. It forms rose-red crystals, sparingly soluble in water. {Found: N, 33'29; S, 7'54; Cu, 15'11. [X] $\text{SO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 33'52; S, 7'66; Cu, 15'23 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium thiosulphate was obtained as a pale rose crystalline precipitate by adding a solution of sodium thiosulphate to a concentrated solution of the chloride. {Found: N, 32'65; S, 14'70; Cu, 14'63. [X] $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 32'43; S, 14'82; Cu, 14'73 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium thiocyanate was prepared by heating the copper biguanide base with a solution of ammonium thiocyanate. It forms shining bluish violet crystals, sparingly soluble in water. {Found: S, 16'65; Cu, 16'63. [X] $(\text{SCN})_2$ requires S, 16'77; Cu, 16'66 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium dithionate was prepared by adding a solution of sodium dithionate to a concentrated solution of the chloride. It forms rose-red crystals, soluble in water. {Found: S, 13'72; Cu, 13'88. [X] $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S, 13'86; Cu, 13'77 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium chromate was obtained as a yellow crystalline precipitate from a solution of potassium chromate and the complex chloride. {Found: N, 31'96; Cr, 11'79; Cu, 14'52. [X] $\text{CrO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 32'13; Cr, 11'93; Cu, 14'60 per cent}.

Cupric bisbiguanidinium hypophosphite was precipitated as rose-red crystals by adding a solution of sodium hypophosphite to a concentrated solution of the chloride. {Found: Cu, 14'85; P, 14'42. [X] $(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 14'73; P, 14'36 per cent}.

A solution of the complex chloride gave pale rose, moderately soluble, crystalline precipitate with potassium chlorate, bromate and iodate. Sparingly soluble pale rose precipitates were also obtained with alkali perchlorate and periodate. It also gave characteristic coloured precipitates with a number of complex anions, e.g. ferrocyanide, ferricyanide, cobalticyanide, nitroprusside, thiosulphato-cobalticyanide, disulphito-cobalticyanide, chromithiocyanate, cobaltinitrite, borofluoride, aurichloride, platinumchloride, etc.